

Data Governance Plan for The Energy Access and Modelling Project: Case Study of Primary Energy Consumers in Vietnam

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Executive Summary

This report presents a data governance plan for Vietnam energy modelling and access project. Using case studies of primary energy consumers (PECs) across sectors, the report highlights the relevance and need to establish a comprehensive framework to ensure the accuracy, accessibility and security of energy and geospatial data.

The report applied the Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) tool combined with Geographic Information System (GIS) tools to visualize the characteristics and relationships between the internal factors of the enterprise and the relationship between the enterprise and the existing energy infrastructure system in the localities. On that basis, the report discussed an integrated energy data management process including the approach, integration, construction of data management structure, management policies and standards, security protocols, data encryption; and a plan for sustainable management of databases from PECs.

The report concludes that an effective data governance plan will bring many benefits to stakeholders. Therefore, promoting collaboration, participation and commitment of all stakeholders is key to improving data quality and supporting more accurate decision-making processes.

1. Introduction

The Vietnamese government prioritises the economical and efficient use of energy as a key policy. This approach is crucial for reducing pressure on the national power supply, lowering business operational costs, and enhancing overall economic efficiency in the sector. Accordingly, on September 29, 2020, the Ministry of Industry and Trade (MoIT) issued Circular No. 25/2020/TT-BCT regulating the planning and reporting of energy efficiency plans, as well as conducting energy audits. This Circular stipulates the need to identify a list of primary energy consumers (PEC). This is important in helping state management agencies monitor and supervise energy use, ensure compliance and encourage these establishments to apply energy-saving measures. At the same time, it supports the planning and implementation of energy-saving programs, ensuring that establishments conduct regular energy audits, thereby detecting and correcting problems related to energy efficiency.

To ensure that the implementation of this circular is effective, a comprehensive plan and framework for the management of the collected data is essential. This report focuses on developing such a plan to ensure the accuracy, accessibility, and security of geospatial and energy data, which is critical for the successful planning and implementation of energy access initiatives in Vietnam. Specific objectives include (i) Developing a comprehensive framework to manage and update electricity usage in primary energy; (ii) Enhancing access to energy data, promoting investment opportunities to develop the grid and power sources according to actual needs to ensure energy security, and grid safety and promote economic development.

2. Methodology

2.1. Modeling Approach/Tool Implemented

Attribute data will be collected from reports of production facilities as required by the Ministry of Industry and Trade and cross-checked with data from the Vietnam Electricity Group. On that basis, a list of primary energy consumers by province/city and by region will be made.

Spatial data on production facilities will be collected through GIS and remote sensing tools. Use satellite images and aerial surveys to collect geospatial data; use open data platforms to collect spatial locations (points) of all production/business facilities.

This report applies the Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) tool to show how different entities relate to each other in the database. This helps to visualize the attributes of businesses, their distribution and relationships with socio-economic characteristics and existing energy infrastructure systems.

2.2. Data sources

Primary data will be collected from surveys conducted by the Ministry of Industry and Trade, while secondary data will be collected from Vietnam Electricity, the Ministry of

Planning and Investment, the National Statistics Office, and international energy data sets. The subjects of the collection are production facilities with a total annual energy consumption converted to tons of oil equivalent of over 1,000 TOE and construction works with a total energy consumption of over 500 TOE per year.

Secondary Data: Data obtained from third-party sources such as government databases, academic research, or international organisations.

Open Data Platforms: Publicly available data sources, such as OpenStreetMap, Google Maps, World Bank datasets, or national geospatial data portals.

2.3. Assumptions

All data reported from businesses must meet a 95% accuracy standard as verified against electricity consumption data provided by Vietnam Electricity, and ensure that the datasets used in the modelling are reliable and actionable. The data governance plan will comply with Vietnam's Data Law 2024, Electricity Law 2024 (amended) and align with the GDPR standards.

3. Results

3.1. Develop a comprehensive framework to manage and update energy usage at primary energy consumers

The list of PECs and their energy consumption levels will be updated annually. This result is the basis for developing plans and reporting on the implementation of annual and 5-year plans on energy saving and efficiency of PECs (units with annual electricity consumption of 100,000 kWh or more).

The collected data will show the current status of energy consumption; potential for savings and efficient use; spatial distribution of PECs (including both attribute data and spatial data); and current status of energy supply infrastructure in each locality. *Appendix C* shows the following relationships:

- The relationship between the characteristics of the infrastructure and production of the enterprise and the level of energy consumption;
- The relationship between the consumption situation and the ability to self-produce energy for the energy needs of each facility;
- The relationship between the practical solutions for energy saving and efficiency of the enterprise and the amount of energy consumed;
- The relationship between the energy supply capacity of the local/regional infrastructure system for the needs and operations of the enterprises
- The relationship between the existing energy infrastructure system and the socio-economic development of the locality and region.
- Indicate the level of shortage or the ability to meet the energy needs, the power transmission system for the needs of the locality and region; as well as the need to invest in developing various types of energy systems.

To visualize the collected and managed database, see details in the data description table - *Appendix C*.

3.2. Enhance access to energy data for grid development planning and promote new power source investment

Building a comprehensive framework for collecting, updating, managing and analyzing data from the list of PECs will help stakeholders have opportunities to access energy data most completely. From there, promote the development of plans for developing energy infrastructure systems and investing in power sources (especially renewable energy) by the consumption needs of PECs, in each region. This provides the following values:

- Management and monitoring: Help state management agencies monitor and supervise the energy use of large facilities, ensuring they comply with energy-saving regulations.
- Energy saving: Encourages these facilities to apply energy-saving measures, thereby reducing costs and protecting the environment.
- Planning: Supports the planning and implementation of energy-saving programs more effectively.
- Energy auditing: Ensures that facilities conduct periodic energy audits, thereby detecting and correcting problems related to energy efficiency.
- Investment promotion: Based on the current situation and energy needs of each enterprise, province/city and region, relevant parties can develop appropriate investment and development plans for energy infrastructure networks. Investors can base on the current status and type of energy infrastructure in localities and regions in Vietnam make decisions on choosing production and business locations.

4. Discussion

Data Cleaning and Formatting

Data will undergo a multi-step cleaning process, including outlier detection, standardisation of units to metric, and validation based on enterprise data from the Ministry of Planning & Investment, data on energy infrastructure and electricity consumption from the Ministry of Industry and Trade, Vietnam Electricity Group, and data on population, socio-economics from the General Statistics Office.

Data Integration

Geospatial data from satellite imagery and open sources (point, line, polygon data) will be integrated with demographic, and socio-economic data using a common spatial reference system, enabling comprehensive mapping of large energy consumers and energy infrastructure systems by location.

Data Governance Structure

The Ministry of Industry and Trade will appoint a Data Steward responsible for overseeing the energy access data, ensuring compliance with national standards. Data Custodians from the IT department will manage the data's technical infrastructure, while Data Users, including planners and policymakers, will access the data for energy modelling purposes.

- The Energy Efficiency and Sustainable Development Department (MoIT) is responsible for managing and monitoring data assets, ensuring data quality and compliance.
- Director, The Energy Efficiency and Sustainable Development Department - the final authority for specific data sets.
- The Energy Efficiency and Sustainable Development Department's IT Specialist is responsible for technical data management, including storage, security and backup.
- Departments, Divisions, and Research Institutes use data for analysis, reporting, and decision-making.

A Data Governance Working Group will be established, comprising representatives from the Ministry of Industry and Trade, Ministry of Science and Technology, Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment, representatives of key energy-consuming facilities, and key NGOs. This group will be responsible for developing data policies, ensuring compliance with standards, and facilitating cross-departmental communication.

Governance Policies and Standards

All data reported from businesses must meet a 95% accuracy standard as verified against electricity consumption data provided by Vietnam Electricity, ensuring that the datasets used in the modelling are reliable and actionable.

The data governance plan will comply with Vietnam's Data Law 2024, and Electricity Law 2024 (amended) and align with the GDPR standards for managing personal data, ensuring that all data processes are legally compliant.

Security Protocols

All sensitive data will be encrypted using AES-256 encryption, and access will be controlled via role-based permissions with regular audits to ensure compliance. AES 256-bit encryption is an international standard that ensures superior data security and is recognized by the US government and many other countries. AES 256-bit encryption is virtually impossible to decrypt, making it the strongest encryption standard available today.

Data Encryption

Encryption keys will be managed centrally by the IT department of the Ministry of Industry and Trade, with strict protocols in place to prevent unauthorised access.

Plan for sustainable development

The Ministry of Industry and Trade is responsible for allocating an annual budget to maintain and update the database, ensuring that the data sets are always up-to-date and

relevant. However, to ensure the sustainability and longevity of the data governance framework, it is necessary to promote serious and responsible participation of businesses, local Departments of Industry and Trade and other stakeholders.

Limitations of study

Data governance risk analysis shows that the potential for data breaches is a significant threat in the current context, including the risk of data being hacked or attacked; risks related to systems, human error and the risk of violating corporate data protection regulations.

Potential areas for future research

To ensure that the data system is fully developed and that data is regularly and continuously accessible, it is necessary to have annual surveys or workshops with PECs, local authorities (Departments of Industry and Trade), and other stakeholders to assess the adequacy of the data governance framework. At the same time, data managers are provided with the latest data management tools and techniques.

5. Conclusion

This report has outlined an overall picture of the data governance plan for the energy modelling and access project through the case study of PECs in Vietnam. A comprehensive and holistic framework for energy data of enterprises, localities and regions has been proposed to assess the organic relationship between the components within enterprises as well as the relationship between PECs and the local energy infrastructure system and the socio-economic development in the region. The implementation of such an energy data governance plan brings many benefits to stakeholders including local management agencies, national policymakers, enterprises, investors, NGOs, researchers and the public. Through this, data quality is improved, decision-making is better and cooperation among stakeholders is enhanced.

To further improve the modelling and accessibility of energy data in general and PECs in particular, it is necessary to develop a roadmap with milestones for the process of upgrading the governance framework. One of the important bases to promote this process is to increase the cooperation and commitment from all stakeholders./.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Glossary of Terms

ERD	Entity Relationship Diagram
EVN	Vietnam Electricity
MoIT	Minister of Industry and Trade
PECs	Primary Energy Consumers

Appendix B. Data Governance Structure Diagram

Source: Mosley, Mark, et al. 2010

Appendix C: Data Sources and Database Schema

Entity	Attribute	Description
Enterprise	<p>EnterpriseID (PK)</p> <p>Enterprise name (TEXT)</p> <p>Location (TEXT)</p> <p>Longitude (INT)</p> <p>Latitude (INT)</p> <p>Industry (ENUM)</p> <p>Business sector (TEXT)</p> <p>Energy consumption (FLOAT)</p> <p>Year (INT)</p> <p>Mangement level (ENUM)</p> <p>Geom (GEOMETRY: POINT, 4326)</p> <p>ProvinceID (PK)</p>	<p>Represents an enterprise in a particular province</p> <p>EnterpriseID: Unique identifier for the enterprise</p> <p>Enterprise name: Name of the enterprise</p> <p>Location: Address of the enterprise</p> <p>Longitude: Longitude coordinates</p> <p>Latitude: Latitude coordinates</p> <p>Industry: Energy; Transport; Construction; Industrial processes; Agriculture, forestry and land use; Waste</p> <p>Business sector: Production and business fields</p> <p>Energy consumption: Consumption of converted energy (TOE)</p> <p>Year: refer to report year</p> <p>Mangement level: Department of Industry and Trade; Vietnam Electricity Group</p> <p>Geom: Spatial data representing the geographic boundaries (point) of the enterprise</p> <p>ProvinceID: Unique identifier for the province</p>
Province	<p>ProvinceID (PK)</p> <p>Province name (TEXT)</p> <p>GRDP scale (FLOAT)</p> <p>Economic Growth (FLOAT)</p> <p>Population scale (INT)</p> <p>Geom (GEOMETRY: polygon, 4326)</p> <p>RegionID (PK)</p>	<p>Represents the province in a particular region</p> <p>ProvinceID: Unique identifier for the province</p> <p>Province name: Name of the province</p> <p>GRDP scale: represents the size of the province's GRDP in a year</p> <p>Economic Growth: economic growth rate</p> <p>Population scale: Total population of the whole province</p> <p>Geom: Spatial data representing the geographic boundaries (polygon) of the province</p> <p>RegionID: Unique identifier for the region</p>
Region	<p>RegionID (PK)</p> <p>Province name (TEXT)</p> <p>Population scale (INT)</p> <p>Energy consumption (FLOAT)</p> <p>Geom (GEOMETRY: polygon, 4326)</p>	<p>Represents the region in the database</p> <p>RegionID: Unique identifier for the region</p> <p>Province name: Name of the province</p> <p>Population scale: Total population of the whole region</p> <p>Energy consumption: Consumption of converted energy (TOE)</p> <p>Geom: Spatial data representing the geographic boundaries (polygon) of the region</p>
Existing Infrastructure	<p>ExistingInfrastructureID</p> <p>Infrastructure name (TEXT)</p> <p>Type TEXT (ENUM)</p> <p>Capacity (FLOAT)</p>	<p>Represents the existing infrastructure in the database</p> <p>Unique identifier for the existing infrastructure</p> <p>Infrastructure name: Name of infrastructure</p> <p>Type: Thermal power plants (coal, oil, gas), hydroelectric plants, wind power plants, solar power plants, waste-to-energy plants</p> <p>Capacity: Plant Capacity</p>

	Status (TEXT)	Status: Operating Status
Energy Consumption	<p>EnergyConsumptionID</p> <p>Type (ENUM)</p> <p>Self-produced electricity (FLOAT)</p> <p>Electricity consumption (FLOAT)</p> <p>Fuel consumption (FLOAT)</p> <p>Other enegy (FLOAT)</p> <p>Total consumption FLOAT</p> <p>EnterpriselD</p>	<p>Represents the energy consumption in the enterprise</p> <p>Energy Consumption: Unique identifier for the enterprise</p> <p>Type: Coal, Oil, LPG, Natural GAS, Gasoline, Other Biomass</p> <p>Self-produced electricity: Amount of electricity the business produces itself</p> <p>Electricity consumption: Power consumption per year</p> <p>Fuel consumption: Fuel consumption per year</p> <p>Other enegy: Other enegy consumption per year</p> <p>Total consumption: Total final consumption</p> <p>EnterpriselD: Unique identifier for the enterprise</p>
Production Status	<p>ProductionStatusID</p> <p>Enterprise name (TEXT)</p> <p>Production capacity (INT)</p> <p>Energy consumption by product (FLOAT)</p> <p>Total production area (FLOAT)</p> <p>Energy consumption demand (FLOAT)</p> <p>Energy management model (ENUM)</p>	<p>Represents the production status in the enterprise</p> <p>Production status: Unique identifier for the enterprise</p> <p>Enterprise name: Name of enterprise</p> <p>Production capacity: Product quantity/year</p> <p>Energy consumption by product: Energy consumption per unit of product</p> <p>Total production area: m2</p> <p>Energy consumption demand: Energy consumption demand in year N+1</p> <p>Energy management model: Not applied; Applied energy management model; Applied energy management model according to TCVN: ISO 50001</p>
Energy Solutions	<p>EnergySolutionsID</p> <p>Solution name (TEXT)</p> <p>Solution type (ENUM)</p> <p>Energy saving potential (FLOAT)</p> <p>EnterpriselD</p>	<p>Represents the energy solutions in the enterprise</p> <p>Energy Solutions: Unique identifier for the enterprise</p> <p>Solution name: Name of the solution</p> <p>Solution type: use of renewable energy; energy management system, ...</p> <p>Energy saving potential: Amount of energy saved</p> <p>EnterpriselD: Unique identifier for the enterprise</p>

